

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF SPATIAL ABILITY WITH MENTAL IMAGERY CLOCK TEST: SAMI-CLOCK TEST

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Abstract

The study of cognitive style in imagery distinguishes between object imagery and spatial imagery. Spatial imagery is assessed through performance-based tests that focus, for example, on object visualization in space, spatial transformations, or mental rotation. In contrast, object imagery is measured using subjective questionnaires related to the visual appearance of objects or scenes in terms of their shape, size, figure, and precise colors. The aim of this study was to develop a new spatial visualization test and to examine its psychometric properties. This test focuses on mirror or symmetrical imagery to assess the ability to mentally construct a mirror image, using simple and familiar objects such as clock faces with numbered hours. To carry out the study, 90 university students completed the Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test (SAMI-Clock Test) along with four additional tests measuring spatial visualization and mental rotation. In addition, participants completed two imagery-related questionnaires—one assessing image vividness and the other image control. The results indicated excellent reliability and adequate validity for the SAMI-Clock Test. We consider that this test provides a measure offering a different perspective on spatial imagery, contributing to the enrichment of research related to imagery and spatial perception.

Keywords: spatial ability, mental imagery, psychometric properties, test.

Resumen

El estudio del estilo cognitivo de imagen diferencia entre imagen de objeto e imagen espacial. La imagen espacial se mide a través de test de rendimiento que se centran, por ejemplo, en la visualización de objetos en el espacio, transformaciones espaciales, o rotación espacial, mientras que la imagen de objeto se mide con cuestionarios subjetivos en relación a las apariencias visuales de objetos o escenas en términos de su forma, tamaño, figura y colores precisos. El objetivo de este trabajo fue desarrollar un nuevo test de visualización espacial y estudiar sus propiedades psicométricas. Esta prueba se centra en la imagen simétrica o en espejo para medir la capacidad para construir una imagen vista en espejo, utilizando objetos sencillos y conocidos como son las esferas de relojes con horas. Para llevar a cabo el estudio pasamos a 90 estudiantes universitarios the Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test (SAMI-Clock Test) y cuatro test más que miden visualización y rotación espacial. Además, los participantes también cubrieron dos pruebas de imagen, una de viveza de imagen y la otra de control de imagen. Los resultados indicaron una excelente fiabilidad y adecuada validez del SAMI-Clock Test. Consideramos que esta prueba aporta una medida con una perspectiva diferente de la imagen espacial, lo que implica un enriquecimiento en los estudios relacionados con la imagen y percepción espacial.

Palabras clave: habilidad espacial, imágenes mentales, propiedades psicométricas, test.

Introduction

The study of imagery ability has been approached from various disciplines, with a particular emphasis on the distinction between spatial imagery and object imagery (see Suica et al., 2022). Spatial imagery refers to fairly abstract representations of spatial relationships among objects, parts of objects, object locations in space, object movements, parts of objects, and other complex spatial transformations. In contrast, object imagery is defined as representations of the visual appearance of objects or scenes in terms of their shape, size, figure, and precise colors (Blajenkova et al., 2006, 2009).

Studies focusing on the measurement of spatial thinking identify different factors (see Burton & Fogarty, 2003; Fehringer, 2023). The most commonly analyzed components of mental imagery are visualization and spatial rotation. Spatial imagery ability is typically assessed through performance-based tests, which can be divided into those more closely associated with tasks requiring the mental manipulation of objects—such as the Mental Rotation Test (MRT; Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978) or the rotation of geometric figures on a plane, as in the Spatial Relations subtest of the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA; Thurstone & Thurstone, 2002)—and those focused on the formation of spatial mental images, i.e., spatial visualization, such as the Measure of the Ability to Form Spatial Mental Imagery (MASMI; Campos, 2009, 2013).

Object imagery is often measured through subjective questionnaires assessing image vividness, such as the Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire (VVIQ; Marks, 1973), or the more recent Plymouth Sensory Imagery Questionnaire (Psi-Q; Andrade et al., 2014), both of which evaluate the clarity and vividness of mentally generated images. A widely used measure is also the Gordon Test of Visual Imagery Control (Gordon Test; Richardson, 1969), a subjective test that involves visualizing object features and transforming the mental image. According to Blajenkova et al. (2006), spatial and object imagery are two independent dimensions of visual processing, implying that individuals may excel in one without necessarily being skilled in the other (see also Pérez-Fabello, 2020; Pérez-Fabello et al., 2016, 2018).

On the other hand, research across different fields has shown that spatial imagery is key in areas such as engineering, architecture, and science, whereas object imagery is more relevant in artistic and creative disciplines (Blajenkova et al., 2006; Blazhenkova & Kozhevnikov, 2009; Kozhevnikov et al., 2013; Pérez-Fabello, 2020; Pérez-Fabello et al., 2016, 2018). The benefits of imagery depend on the individual's capacity to generate mental images (Munzert & Krüger, 2013), and it is considered essential to assess imagery abilities before implementing any enhancement program (Cumming & Ramsey, 2009).

The aim of this study was to develop a new spatial visualization test and to examine its psychometric properties. This test assesses spatial ability through the creation of symmetrical or mirror images of simple and familiar objects, such as clock faces with numbered hours. The Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test (SAMI-Clock Test) emerged in response to the need to continue developing spatial imagery assessments with strong psychometric properties.

Method

Participants

A total of 90 undergraduate students from the Fine Arts program at the University of Vigo, Spain (15 men, 72 women, and 3 identifying as other), with a mean age of 19.61 years ($SD = 1.49$), ranging from 18 to 24 years, participated in the study. All students volunteered to participate freely.

Materials

The Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test (SAMI-Clock Test; see Appendix) was designed to measure spatial ability through the creation of mental images. It consists of 15 model images representing a clock face indicating a specific time, accompanied by four answer options, each showing a different clock image. One of these is the mirror image of the model clock. Participants are required to mentally generate the mirror image and circle the correct answer. Thus, they must mentally reverse the model image. Individual scores are calculated by adding the number of correct responses and subtracting the number of incorrect ones (unanswered questions are not considered), yielding a possible total score ranging from -15 to 15. The correct answers for the test are: 1-B, 2-A, 3-D, 4-B, 5-A, 6-C, 7-B, 8-D, 9-A, 10-B, 11-A, 12-C, 13-D, 14-B, 15-A. The time limit for completing the test is one and a half minutes.

The Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test; Pérez-Fabello, 2025) consists of 18 items involving images of hands in different positions. Each item presents a model image and four alternatives similar to the model but rotated in space—two in the same position as the model and two in a mirror-reversed position. Participants must mentally rotate each option and identify the two that match the model, circling them. Individual scores are calculated by adding correct responses and subtracting incorrect ones (unanswered items are not considered), resulting in a possible score range from -36 to 36. The test duration is one and a half minutes. Pérez-Fabello (2025) reported a Cronbach's alpha of .87.

The Measure of the Ability to Form Spatial Mental Imagery (MASMI; Campos, 2009, 2013)

consists of a decomposed cube that participants must mentally close in order to answer each of the 23 questions. Each item has four options, two of which are correct and two incorrect. The total score is calculated by adding correct answers and subtracting incorrect ones, with possible scores ranging from -46 to 46. Participants have five minutes to complete the test. Campos (2009, 2013) reported Cronbach's alphas of .93 and .90, respectively.

The Spatial Scale of the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA; Thurstone & Thurstone, 2002) measures the ability to imagine and conceptualize objects in two or three dimensions. The test includes 20 items, each presenting a two-dimensional geometric model and six similar figures. Participants must identify which of the six figures match the model, even if they have been rotated on the same plane. The test duration is five minutes. A Cronbach's alpha of .93 was reported (Thurstone & Thurstone, 2002). Ramírez-Uclés and Ramírez-Uclés (2020) reported a Cronbach's alpha of .89.

The Mental Rotation Test (MRT; Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978) consists of 10 items assessing the ability to mentally rotate objects. Each item presents a model and four response options—two correct and two incorrect. Participants were given three minutes to rotate each figure along its axis to determine whether it matched the model. Vandenberg and Kuse (1978) recommend scoring two points when both correct options are selected, zero points if one correct and one incorrect (or both incorrect) options are chosen, and one point if only one option is selected, and it is correct. Scores can range from 0 to 20. Vandenberg and Kuse (1978) reported a test-retest reliability of .83, while Rahe and Quaiser-Pohl (2019) found a Cronbach's alpha of .72.

The Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020) of the Plymouth Sensory Imagery Questionnaire (Psi-Q; Andrade et al., 2014) contains 35 items measuring the vividness of mental imagery across seven sensory modalities: vision, sound, smell, taste, touch, bodily sensation, and emotional feeling. Each modality is represented by five items, and each is rated on a scale from 1 (no image) to 7 (as vivid as real life). The visual modality refers to appearance, e.g., "a cat climbing a tree." The auditory modality begins with "imagine the sound of..." e.g., "hands clapping in applause." The olfactory modality begins with "imagine the smell of..." e.g., "a rose." The gustatory modality starts with "imagine the taste of..." e.g., "lemon." The tactile modality begins with "imagine touching..." e.g., "icy water." The bodily sensation modality begins with "imagine the bodily sensation of..." e.g., "relaxing in a warm bath." Finally, the emotional feeling modality begins with "imagine feeling..." e.g., "in love." The Cronbach's alpha for the Psi-Q was .92 (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020).

The Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2004) of the Gordon Test of Visual Imagery

Control (Gordon Test; Richardson, 1969) measures participants' ability to control visual images. It consists of 12 items that ask participants to imagine a car in different colors, positions, and movement states. Participants then rate each response on a 3-point scale: "no" = 0, "unsure" = 1, and "yes" = 2. Total scores range from 0 to 24, with higher scores indicating greater imagery control. Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2004) reported a Cronbach's alpha of .69.

Procedure

Participants, in groups of approximately 20, completed the following questionnaires at their regular classrooms: the Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test (SAMI-Clock Test), the Hands Test to Measure Rotation Ability with Mental Imagery (RAMI-Hands Test; Pérez-Fabello, in press), the Measure of the Ability to Form Spatial Mental Imagery (MASMI; Campos, 2009, 2013), the Spatial Scale of the Primary Mental Abilities Test (PMA; Thurstone & Thurstone, 1962/2002), the Mental Rotation Test (MRT; Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978), the Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020) of the Plymouth Sensory Imagery Questionnaire (Psi-Q; Andrade et al., 2014), and the Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2004) of the Gordon Test of Visual Imagery Control (Gordon Test; Richardson, 1969). The order of the tests was counterbalanced.

All students were assured that their results would remain anonymous and confidential, and written informed consent was obtained from each participant. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Bioethics Committee of the University of Vigo.

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS 25.0 software program and IBM SPSS Amos 25. The internal consistency of the tests was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. Descriptive statistics were calculated for all measures, and finally, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients were computed to examine the relationship between the SAMI-Clock Test and the other imagery measures. El subapartado Procedimiento resumirá cada paso de la investigación, incluyendo la descripción del espacio, las instrucciones, la formación de los grupos, la manipulación y/o el control de las variables. La sección terminará con un párrafo sobre los métodos utilizados para analizar los datos, aunque si fueran especialmente complejos y requirieran una descripción más detallada se podrá incluir otra subparte específica.

Results and Discussion

First, we analyzed the reliability of the tests used. The internal consistency of the SAMI-Clock Test, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, was .90. According to George and Mallery (2003) and Oviedo and Campo-Arias (2005), this value indicates excellent internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha values for the other tests were as follows: RAMI-Hands Test ($\alpha = .86$), very similar to the .87 reported by Pérez-Fabello (2025); MASMI ($\alpha = .90$), slightly lower than the .93 reported by Campos (2009, 2013) or the .92 reported by Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2023a); PMA ($\alpha = .92$), comparable to previous findings (.93, Thurstone & Thurstone, 2002; .89, Ramírez-Uclés & Ramírez-Uclés, 2020); MRT ($\alpha = .79$), somewhat lower than the .83 reported in the original study by Vandenberg and Kuse (1978); Psi-Q ($\alpha = .94$), similar to the .92 obtained by the Spanish version (Pérez-Fabello & Campos, 2020); and finally, the Gordon Test ($\alpha = .84$), similar to the .87 reported by Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2024), and higher than the .69 obtained by Pérez-Fabello (2004), as well as the .68 and .71 reported by Pérez-Fabello and Campos (2023a, 2023b), respectively.

As can be seen, the instruments used in this study demonstrated very good internal consistency, all falling within the recommended range of .70 to .90 (Oviedo & Campo-Arias, 2005). Descriptive statistics for the measures used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.*Descriptive Statistics for the Measures Used in Study*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Minimum	Maximum
SAMI-Clock Test	9.49	5.67	-6	15
RAMI-Hands Test	14.21	6.65	1	34
MASMI	10.09	10.46	-4	36
MRT	9.81	5.19	0	20
PMA	28.97	14.51	-8	53
Gordon Test	22.03	3.45	4	24
Psi-Q	5.32	0.91	2,51	7

The Pearson product-moment correlations between the SAMI-Clock Test and the other mental imagery measures are shown in Table 2. The SAMI-Clock Test was significantly correlated with the RAMI-Hands Test, MRT, and PMA, all of which assess spatial rotation. A significant correlation was also found between the SAMI-Clock Test and the MASMI, a test that measures the formation of spatial mental imagery. Previous studies have reported similar correlations with spatial imagery and mental rotation tests (Blajenkova et al., 2006; Burton & Fogarty, 2003; Campos, 2009; Kozhevnikov et al., 2002; Pérez-Fabello, in press; Poltrock & Brown, 1984; Richardson, 1977).

Table 2.*The Pearson Product-Moment Correlations Between the SAMI-Clock Test and the Other Measures of Imagery*

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. SAMI-Clock Test						
2. RAMI-Hands Test	.26*					
3. MASMI	.44***	.58***				
4. MRT	.41**	.52***	.72***			
5. PMA	.33**	.77***	.64***	.65***		
6. Gordon Test	-.15	-.12	-.19	-.01	-.13	
7 Psi-Q	.01	-.19	-.11	-.23	-.15	.43***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

The correlations between the SAMI-Clock Test and the imagery questionnaires (Gordon Test and Psi-Q) were weak and non-significant, confirming the results of previous studies that also failed to find significant correlations between spatial visualization tests and imagery vividness questionnaires (Blajenkova et al., 2006; Burton & Fogarty, 2003; Campos, 2009; Pérez-Fabello, in press; Poltrock & Brown, 1984; Richardson, 1977). This once again supports the notion that object imagery and spatial imagery measure distinct cognitive processes.

The SAMI-Clock Test demonstrated high reliability and validity, comparable to that found in other spatial imagery tests, such as the MASMI and the MRT, both of which have been identified as adequate tools (Suica et al., 2022). With this study, we contribute a valuable addition to the assessment of mental imagery by introducing a new spatial imagery test.

A limitation of the present study is the restriction of the sample to a university population, as well as the number of participants which, although sufficient for the analyses conducted, does not allow for the development of norms by gender or age groups. The novelty of this test lies in its use of mirror or symmetrical imagery, offering a unique perspective within the field of spatial imagery assessment.

We believe that this measure can enrich research related to mental imagery and spatial perception; however, further studies are needed to strengthen the current findings. It is essential to apply this test to more diverse populations to enhance its applicability across different contexts and disciplines. Additionally, administering this test to students in primary and secondary education would also be of interest.

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Appendix

Spatial Ability with Mental Imagery Clock Test: SAMI-Clock Test.

You are now going to see the image of a clock showing a specific time. The thick hand indicates the hour, and the thin hand indicates the minutes. On the left side, you will see a model clock showing a specific time. Your task is to identify which alternative – A, B, C, or D – corresponds to the mirror image of the model. That is, the left side would appear on the right, and the right side would appear on the left. There is only one correct answer, which you must circle.

Now, let's look at an example: Which of the following options is the mirror image of the model?

You need to mentally visualize the mirror image of the model clock in order to determine the correct answer. The correct answer is A, so a circle is drawn around the letter A. Please note that there is only one correct answer for each item, and incorrect answers will be subtracted from the total score. Therefore, do not mark an answer unless you are fairly certain it is correct – you may leave it blank and return to it later. When instructed, turn the page and begin. You will have 1 minute and 30 seconds to complete the test.

DO NOT TURN THE PAGE UNTIL YOU ARE TOLD TO DO SO.

	MODEL	OPTION A	OPTION B	OPTION C	OPTION D
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					

7		A	B	C	D
8		A	B	C	D
9		A	B	C	D
10		A	B	C	D
11		A	B	C	D
12		A	B	C	D
13		A	B	C	D

